

Human Resources Development Strategies for Building Sustainability of the Indian Tourism Sector

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Introduction

Human resources development in the tourism industry experiences from a divergence of views held by the key players, such as employers, employees, and training providers. Quoting from 'PA Consulting Group's research on tourism training in Scotland,' Brogan lists these divergences in views, '. . . That employers did not see the business benefit of investing in their employees who were often part-time, temporary, and viewed as low-calibre. Employers and candidates perceived tourism jobs as having little status, poor conditions, and low pay. Training providers saw tourism businesses as being apathetic about training and provided what they could rather than what was required.' The lack of concern or indifference is felt mostly in the context of the institutional framework for HRD in tourism. Lack of adequately trained instructors has always been a significant issue at all levels of tourism education and training. As Pollock and Ritchie argue, 'it is not adequate to assume that faculties teaching generic business skills are competent to deliver tourism programs without taking the time to understand and master the complexities of this industry.'

Human Resources Development and Sustainability

The growing incidence of environmental problems and the resultant discussions and concerns regarding environmental conservation in the 1980s gave birth to the theory of sustainability, sustainable development, and sustainable tourism development. As in the general ecological discourse, there is an abundance of principles, codes, and guidelines for sustainability in the tourism industry.

However, the concepts and methods of sustainability are mired in contradictions and controversies. To start with, sustainable development contains 'two seemingly paradoxical aspects, namely, preservation and development.' Another critical problem that makes the entire theory suspect is its exploitation by the tourism industry by resorting to what is identified as 'eco-labelling and eco-selling.' As MacLellan argues, 'in many cases, sustainable tourism policies

give the appearance of significant change in attitude while in reality, they make little impact on underlying trends and institutional structures. Governments have become adept at devising tactics that produce changes at the ‘margins’ or ‘one tuning,’ rather than making fundamental policy shifts.’ However, as Wall argues ‘to the extent that the concepts engender a Long-term vision, encourage the search for, foster notions of equity and evaluation of types of tourism, promote an appreciation of the importance of inter-sectoral linkages, and facilitate dialogue between individuals and groups whose perspectives might at sight appear to be at odds, they sustainable construction methods are useful catalysts in the search for more benign kinds of tourism which are likely to contribute to long-term development, broadly conceived’. Given the importance of human resources in the tourism industry, sustainability has a specific HRD dimension. According to Lane, ‘imported employees ‘and ‘lack of career structure’ are among the features of non-sustainable tourism. Also, the to, the tourism industry is notorious for its poor image as an employer, with its seasonality, low wages, poor working conditions, lack of any adequately planning or laid down the career ladder, ad hoc recruitment practices and indifference to training and development. Considering the ‘people dimension’ of the tourism business, the key to sustainability is the people who are involved in the tourism service providers, the industry as guests, and the hosts. It is their awareness of the attitudes, sustainability issues, perceptions, expectations, and value system that would make a true impact on how the tourism industry is run and its environmental impacts. Even if there are policies and well thought-out plans are trying at sustainability they will be of no value if they cannot be rendered into reality and this would require the commitment and involvement of people at all levels. Human resources development has a vital role in improving sustainability; as education can lead to more clarity concerning sustainability issues, develop a realistic image of tourism and, more importantly, help build sustainability oriented professional ‘ethics’ and ‘sub-culture’ within the tourism industry. It would not be inaccurate to conclude that the exclusion of human resources as the centre of such policies has been one of the causes of performing these efforts ineffective. Both from the development and preservation angle, HRD holds the key to sustainability. Development needs a higher level of quality, and preservation requires attitudes, sensitivities, and practices that are responsible for and appropriate for the environment, local society, culture, and economy. Both development and maintenance fall strictly within the HRD domain. The sustainability oriented HRD programs will have the concepts and practices of sustainability as the primary focus.

This paper attempts to provide a sense of human resources development (HRD) for tourism in south India inside the structure of sustainability. Establishing the link between sustainability and HRD in tourism, it identifies various target groups for the sustainability-oriented HRD programs and the multiple levels at which such applications are to be carried out.

A Myopic View of Indian Tourism

Even though global tourism grew at a very rapid pace during the post-war period, Indian tourism has not only been unable to keep pace with this growth rate but has underperformed in its development, especially in comparison with other countries in the region such as Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand and Singapore , which started developing tourism simultaneously with India. Whereas world tourist visitors grew from 25 million in 1950 to 613 million in 1997, in India international tourist arrivals developed from 17000 in 1951 to only 2.37 million in 1997, which means a share of less than 0.4% of the world international tourist arrivals. As far as the earnings are concerned, India received just US\$ 3.1 billion out of a world total of US\$ 444 billion. Considering the geographical area and diversity, cultural heritage, tourist attractions and resources, and the reasonably developed infrastructure that it maintains the performance of Indian tourism has been very sluggish. Middle class, which is already more than 250 million, more and more

Indians now take annual holidays, which augurs well for domestic tourism. The expected high growth rate of tourism in the coming decades and possible saturation in hitherto well-established tourism destinations in Western Europe offer a perfect opportunity for Indian tourism to tap its potential for development. Moreover, the emergence of ‘the new tourism, which is defined by modern tourists, new technology, sustainable growth, segmented markets and diagonal integration; driven by consumers, who are more experienced, spontaneous and flexible, with changed values, demographics and life styles, and more interested in adventure, environment, and culture; and driven by technologies that are integrated, flexible, value-oriented, friendly, rapidly diffused, system oriented and easy accessibility are offering productive potential for further growth and development for Indian tourism sector.

Human Resources Development Strategies for Indian Tourism Sector

Practical concerns for HRD in tourism has a relatively recent origin in India, beginning with the opening of the College of Catering and Institutional Management in Bombay in 1954, with the United Nations funding. This was followed by three more regional institutions, in Calcutta, Delhi, and Madras, in 1962, and 12 food craft centres in different parts of the country. The main focus of these institutions, however, was food and nutrition rather than hospitality and, the reason being that the then priority of overcoming the problems of starvation and malnutrition that confronted the country during its post-independence days. These institutions were only transferred to the Ministry of Tourism in 1982, and in 1984 a national umbrella organization, the National Council for Hotel Management (NCHM) was created as the apex body for hospitality education. Currently, there are 16 Institutes of Hotel Management (IHM), training personnel for middle management and craft levels and 15 Food Craft Institutes (FCI), providing training in specific areas such as cookery, house keeping, restaurant and counter service, bakery, reception, etc. In addition to these, major hotel companies such as Taj, Oberoi and Welcome group in the private sector and the Indian Tourism Development Corporation (ITDC) in the public sector have set up their training institutions. Recent years have also seen several training institutions developing in the private sector, some of them with adequate infrastructure but a good number with commercial motives and hence questionable credentials and inadequate facilities. There are also apprenticeship schemes focusing on craft training, mainly in major hotel companies and tourism development corporations, ranging from 6 months to 2 years duration, but with no external recognition through certification.

The most important achievement in this road was launching of tourism courses in the universities by offering assistance in curriculum design, especially for the Master level program in Tourism Administration (MTA), which was started in 1991 in Kurukshetra University, and lobbying with the Universities Grant Commission (UGC), which resulted in the UGC financing introduction inclusion of tourism courses in 25 institutions all over the country. Currently, there are 24 universities offering a postgraduate degree or diploma courses, 21 universities having affiliated colleges offering tourism as a subject in undergraduate courses, 37 colleges offering tourism as a vocational subject at the undergraduate level, and 11 polytechnics and other institutions providing tourism courses in the country.

Human Resources Development and Sustainability in Indian Tourism Sector

Discussing HRD implications for sustainable socio-cultural tourism Pearce, lists empowering visitors, training tourism professionals, and educating host communities as strategies for ‘ecologically sustainable socio-cultural tourism development.’ These strategies are relevant not just about socio-cultural issues but have important implications for the problems of overall sustainability in tourism. The attitudes, value systems, expectations, experiences, and sensitivity of these groups are essential variables in ensuring sustainability oriented tourism development.

Therefore HRD strategies aiming at sustainability have to adopt a three-dimensional approach focusing on tourism industry personnel, the host community, and the tourists. Tourism industry personnel: The tourism industry is characterized by a wide variety, and different patterns of employment is often a very challenging proposition. As Burns points out, 'these range from the clear cut divisions of labour and heavily unionized airline sector, the clearly defined contracts and conditions of service by international corporations such as Ramada Renaissance and Sheraton, the minimum wage, short contract, insecure conditions that characterize much of catering work to the working in bars in any one of a number of tourist traps around the world'. The hundreds of self-employed individual small-time vendors also could be added to this list.

The efficiency, competence, and the value system of human resources are very vital for the total quality of a country's tourism. Quality is important in the sustainability context too. Quality of tourist experiences is related directly to the physical, social, and cultural environments of tourist destinations.

Ensuring this vital aspect of tourism development would result in the sustainability of tourism destinations, from both the development and preservation angle. From both the development and maintenance perspective, tourism industry personnel can contribute to sustainability. The importance of service quality in enhancing the quality of visitor experience and for competitive advantage is widely recognised Human resources development can also contribute to sustainability-oriented practices, especially within the 'internal environment' of any tourism operation, which will help to conservation. At all levels, HRD can play an essential role in bringing such practices to the realm of daily activities and a part of the work culture.

Within the hospitality sector, the 3 R's (reduce, reuse, recycle) are increasingly becoming a common practice. Besides promoting and supporting good, environmentally responsible practices, these measures would also result in more profitability for the firm.

TEDQUAL methodology, which strives to instil a 'culture of service quality,' could play an essential role in the sustainability context also. The model could be used to disseminate concepts and practices of sustainability and to develop a 'culture of sustainability' in the tourism industry. The role of tour operators, as 'interpreters and coordinators of the tourism market and in making tourism an agent of sustainability cannot be stressed.

A sustainability-oriented approach to pre-employment training involves the forecasting of skills requirement, both in qualitative and quantitative terms and provision of relevant infrastructure in locations where this personnel would be required. The training inputs and methods would need to have a strong underpinning of sustainability values and practices and hence are often not included in HRD, leading to the perception of tourism jobs as unskilled and semi-skilled. As Indian tourism has its significant markets in the western world, provision of soft competencies, which include language skills, hospitality etiquette, communication and time management skills and the familiarity with the 'low context culture' come under the skills category to be included in tourism training.

Pollock and Ritchie present a model of tourism occupations at four levels, namely, front-line, supervisory, management, and senior executive, which are to be found in all the major sectors of the tourism industry. Sio has suggested a model of training and development infrastructure, which includes different layers in the education system, such as universities, colleges, institutions of higher learning, technical institutions, junior colleges, secondary schools, primary schools, and adult literacy programs, etc., to carry out various types of training. These models do have implications for pre-employment HRD activities in Indian tourism, and the infrastructure proposed by Sio is already in place in India and could efficiently be utilised for tourism training.

Some of the significant issues in the pre-employment training domain include the ‘coverage of tourism within the school curriculum,’ ‘structure of vocational and professional courses and qualifications,’ ‘links between education and tourism industry’ and ‘academic qualification in tourism and hospitality’ These issues are essential in the context of sustainable HRD practices and hence merit analysis in the Indian situation.

Coverage of Tourism within the School Curriculum

Tourism can readily be included in the school curriculum at all levels, primarily as it can be delivered as part of many established subject areas, such as geography, economics, or history. It would not only help create tourism awareness but also attract students at an early stage to a career in tourism by creating a better image of the industry and thus drawing better talent. As far as the condition in India is concerned tourism is yet to be included in the school curriculum at the national level, except the State of Kerala, where tourism finds a place in the recently introduced ‘Vocational Higher Secondary Education.’ Tourism is available in four such Vocational Higher Secondary Schools, and more schools are in the process of adding tourism courses at this level. However, tourism at this level attracts only those who do not get admission to other vocational streams, such as civil engineering and laboratory technician courses, with obvious implications on the quality of students and their interest in the subject. The curriculum offered at this level is also too theoretical and general.

Moreover, this may just be a passing phase in the educational process of the students, as a good number of them may not pursue further education in tourism and end up in traditional undergraduate programs. As the quality of intake is poor and there are limitations in curriculum and infrastructure, employability of those coming out from this stream is severely limited. However, as a beginning, this has the potential to be developed into a more standardized program and to be introduced as one of the strands in higher secondary education throughout the country.

The international best practices in the area are those that were established under the auspices of American Express and styled the ‘Global Travel and Tourism Programme’ (GTTP), which is present in Brazil, Canada, Hong Kong, Hungary, Ireland, Mexico, Russia, South Africa, and the UK. Programs under GTTP are designed to satisfy student educational needs, industry workforce needs, and educational system resource needs. Some of the models of international practices, offering tourism education at the school level, can be adapted to suit the Indian situation, especially the systems in Ireland and the UK. As the necessary foundation is already in place, including an awarding body, namely, Board of Technical Education, the widespread introduction of tourism in the school curriculum is both pragmatic and relevant.

Vocational and Professional Courses and Qualifications

It is widely held that the provision of vocational courses and professional courses in tourism and hospitality has to be carried out by sector- dedicated institutions and programs, as these have the most prominent role in meeting the industry’s human resource needs. As the STRU report points out, however, the primary issue confronting the provision of education and training in tourism and, in particular, the structure of such provision, is one of appropriate matching between the current and projected needs of the tourism sector and the duration, level and focus of the education and training which is available’. A multitude of stakeholders with conflicting and diverse views make the situation more complicated. Human resources development strategies with human resources planning as the starting point would help in streamlining the system and avoiding conflicts. However, there are several examples of vocational and professional streams of tourism training organised and managed by dedicated institutional organisations in many countries in an effective manner.

In India two national level bodies, namely, the National Council of Hotel Management (NCHM) and the Indian Institute of Travel Management (IITTM) and Tourism, look after this stream. The 16 Institutes of Hotel Management (IHM) and 15 Food Craft Institutes (FCI) cater to the human resources requirement of the hospitality sector, with the IHMs training personnel for the skilled, supervisory, middle management and training positions and FCIs offering training in specific crafts. However, the out-turn is far short of the industry requirements, in spite of the extra efforts by private sector institutions. The IITTM offers Diploma programs at its headquarters and through its regional chapters for careers in the tourism and travel sector.

Regional institutions, such as the Kerala Institute of Tourism and Travel Studies (KITTS), in South India, offer their Diploma and Certificate courses to cater to the human resources requirements of the tourism industry in the region. The KITTS has been successful in developing a variety of courses dealing with specific operational and management areas of the tourism industry in the region, including entrepreneurship development programs. There is no national planning and training model in place in India to compare with that in Ireland through the Council for Education, Recruitment, and Training (CERT). Education and training programs that match the present and future priorities of Indian tourism, rather than with a general focus, would make the human resources and the tourism industry more responsive to the challenges ahead. Some of the specific areas of importance for Indian tourism include activity holidays, cultural tourism, heritage tourism, conference and convention tourism, wildlife tourism, health tourism, rural tourism, and event management. Moreover, indigenization of the curriculum and training methodology to suit the political and regional situation and priorities also may be necessary, especially as there has been a great deal of borrowing from the developed western countries, which could undermine the relevance of the provision. Some international best practice models offer useful strategies for the vocational strand of HRD for tourism in India.

The Host Community

Human Resources Development of personnel come in direct contact with the visitors have to be a significant target, especially considering the dynamics of guest-host encounters. Conventional methods include extension programs aimed at people who are likely to interact with the tourists, effective use of media for creating tourism awareness, adult education, and tourism awareness through the endless stream of knowledge. One reason why tourism education through the universities and schools should be continued and expanded, despite their shortcomings, is their potential to create tourism awareness and in preparing the host community to accept and adjust to tourism. As far as the extension programs are concerned, initiatives may have to be made by the dedicated vocational and professional training institutions. The target groups here would include customs and immigration officials, tourist taxi drivers, police, and any other category of people who are likely to encounter tourists in their day-to-day life. There are many good examples of this at the international level. ‘Welcome Host,’ a short training program in basic customer care in the UK aimed at creating hospitality-oriented attitudes is one such model, worth emulating.

As far as India is concerned, the Indian Institute of Tourism and Travel Management (IITTM) and the Kerala Institute of Tourism and Travel Studies (KITTS) organise such extension programs regularly for the customs and immigration personnel, tourist taxi drivers, tourist police, tourism information personnel, etc. However, these programs need full geographical spread to be more productive. Adult education programs, which offer an active forum for tourism education, would help in creating tourism awareness in India, where adult literacy programs are still going on. The critical role of the voluntary sector here cannot be overemphasised, as the literacy campaign in Kerala, where 100 per cent literacy was achieved in the late 1980s through an intensive literacy

campaign carried out mainly by the voluntary organisations, has proved. Media, both print and electronic, do play a prominent role in spreading information and Knowledge about tourism, sometimes even bordering on activism. Media coverage often takes place without any deliberate efforts from the tourism sector, but the industry could take an active interest in this form of awareness creation by resorting to various types of public relations exercises involving the media. Another major issue in the Indian context is the cultural and traditional barriers to employment in tourism, which has severe implications for HRD in general and host community oriented HRD programs in particular. As Andrews points out, there is traditional family antipathy to work within the hospitality sector, which to some religious and cultural groups, had and still retains images of servitude and menial, demeaning employment. These cultural reservations and prejudices are more acute when it comes to women taking up work tourism sector and in the hospitality, especially in jobs involving customer contact. Changing this negative attitude towards employment in tourism is a significant challenge for HRD in Indian tourism. Host community education can have a very vital role in this, and it is an area where all sectors of tourism public, private, and voluntary need to come together.

The Tourists

As the most critical players in the tourism industry, tourists are frequently blamed for most of the negative consequences of tourism. Tourists generally are strangers to the tourism destinations, its environment and culture. Most of their behaviour that offends the host culture or harms the local environment could be due to their ignorance. Even the well-meaning and innocuous activities of tourists sometimes result in undesirable consequences. At the same time, there are also tourists who tend to take the destination communities, especially in the developing world and peripheral areas, for granted. It is essential to educate tourist about the destination, its environment, society, and local customs to be observed, and regarding acceptable and responsible behaviour at the destination. Such knowledge can avert or minimize a large number of negative socio-cultural and environmental impacts and contribute to sustainability.

Foreign citizens who visit India to study, work or act as missionaries, do research, as well as all travellers generally within 14 days of arrival, planning to stay more than 180 days, are expected to register, with the Foreigners Regional Registration Office (FRRO) nearest to where they will be staying. The FRRO maintains offices in New Delhi, Chennai, Mumbai (known as the “Chennai Immigration Office”), Amritsar and Kolkata. In smaller towns and cities, the local police headquarters will typically perform this role (related to as the Foreigner’s Registration Office or FRO). General information regarding immigration rules and Indian visa, including the telephone numbers and addresses for the FRRO offices, can be located at the Indian Ministry of Home Affairs website for its Bureau of Immigration at <http://www.immigrationindia.nic.in>.

If a foreign citizen (e.g., an American) overstays his or her Indian visa or otherwise violates Indian visa regulations, the traveller may require a clearance from the Ministry of Home Affairs to leave the country. Such travellers generally must in some cases and pay a fine, may be jailed until their deportation can be arranged. Visa violators seeking an exit clearance can visit the following office any weekday from 10 am - 12 noon: Ministry of Home Affairs, Foreigners Division, Jaisalmer House, 26 Man Singh Road, New Delhi 110 011 (tel. +91-11-2338-5748).

Safety and Security

Several anti-Western terrorist groups (some of which are on the U.S. government’s list of foreign terrorist organizations are believed to be active in India., including, but not limited to, Islamic extremist groups such as Harakat ul-Mujahidin, Jaish-e-Mohammed, and Lashkar-e Tayyiba.

While historically Jammu and Kashmir have been a focal point of terrorist activity, bomb blasts resulting in deaths and injuries have occurred in public places such as markets, as well as on public transportation such as trains and buses throughout India. Examples of significant attacks in recent years include the detonation of explosive devices on a train northwest of Delhi (February 2007), simultaneous attacks on Mumbai commuter trains (July 2006), simultaneous attacks on a train station and places of worship in Varanasi (March 2006), and simultaneous attacks on several markets in New Delhi (October 2005). Several other terrorist incidents causing fewer casualties have also occurred, including a few in which American citizens were injured. The motive for many of these attacks has not been established, although it is believed that U.S. citizens were not specifically targeted or damaged in any of these attacks. Specific areas of concern are addressed below under “Areas of Instability.” Beyond the threat from terrorism, demonstrations are also likely to cause disruption. Protests can begin spontaneously and escalate with little warning, disrupting transportation systems and city services and posing risks to travellers’ safety. In response to such events, Indian authorities occasionally impose curfews and restrict travel. U.S. citizens are urged to avoid demonstrations and rallies as they have the potential for violence, especially immediately preceding and following elections. Also, religious and inter-caste violence is unpredictable and occurs occasionally.

In some cases, demonstrators specifically block roads near popular tourist sites to gain the attention of Indian authorities, although tourists are rarely attacked in these incidents. Mobs have, however, attacked Indian and American missionaries and social workers as such activity provokes strong reactions in some areas. U.S. citizens should monitor local television and print media and contact the U.S. Embassy or the nearest U.S. Consulate for further information about the current situation in areas where they wish to travel.

Finally, visitors should exercise caution when swimming in open waters along the Indian coastline, particularly during the monsoon season. Every year, several people in Goa, Mumbai, Puri (Orissa), and other areas drown due to the strong undertow. It is essential for visitors to heed warnings posted or advised at beaches and avoid swimming in the ocean during the monsoon season.

Areas of Instability

Jammu & Kashmir: The Department of State recommends that U.S. citizens avoid travel to the state of Jammu & Kashmir, except visits to the eastern Ladakh region and its capital, Leh. Several terrorist groups operate in the country, targeting security forces that are present throughout the region, particularly along the Line of Control (LOC) separating Indian and Pakistani-controlled Kashmir, and those stationed in the primary tourist destinations in the Kashmir Valley - Srinagar, Gulmarg, and Pahalgam.

Since 1989, as many as 60,000 people (terrorists, security forces, and civilians) have been killed in the Kashmir conflict. Many terrorist incidents take place in the state’s summer capital of Srinagar, but the majority of attacks occur in rural areas. Foreigners are particularly visible, vulnerable, and definitely at risk. Furthermore, attacks have been aimed at civilians with increasing frequency. For example, in 2006, several grenade attacks were launched against buses carrying local tourists. The Indian government prohibits foreign tourists from visiting certain areas along the LOC (see the section on Restricted Areas, below). U.S. Government employees are prohibited from travelling to the state of Jammu & Kashmir (except for Ladakh) without permission from the U.S. Embassy in New Delhi.

India-Pakistan Border: The State Department recommends that U.S. citizens avoid travel to areas within five to ten kilometres of the border between India and Pakistan. Both India and Pakistan

maintain a strong military presence on both sides of the border. The only official India-Pakistan border crossing point for persons who are not citizens of India or Pakistan is in the state of Punjab between Atari, India, and Wagah, Pakistan. A Pakistani visa is required to enter Pakistan. The border crossing is usually open, but travellers are advised to confirm the current status of the border crossing before commencing travel.

Both India and Pakistan claim an area of the Karakoram mountain range that includes the Siachen glacier. U.S. citizens travelling to or climbing peaks in the disputed regions face significant risks. The disputed area consists of the following heights: Rimo Peak; Apsarasas I, II, and III; Tegam Kangri I, II and III; Suingri Kangri; Giant I and II; Indira Col; and Sia Kangri. Travellers may check with the U.S. Embassy in New Delhi for information on current conditions

Northeast States: Sporadic incidents of violence by ethnic insurgent groups, including the bombing of buses and trains, have been reported in parts of Assam, Manipur, Nagaland, Tripura, and Meghalaya. While U.S. citizens have not been specifically targeted, they may be affected as bystanders. Visitors to India's Northeast states are cautioned not to travel outside major cities at night. Security laws are in force, and the central government has deployed security personnel. Individual Northeastern states can be visited by foreigners only with a permit. Travelers may check with the U.S. Consulate in Kolkata for information on current conditions.

East Central and Southern India: Self-styled Maoist extremist groups called "Naxalites" are active in the region, primarily in rural areas. The Naxalites have a long history of conflict with state and national authorities, including attacks on police and government officials. The Naxalites have not specifically targeted U.S. citizens, but have attacked symbolic targets that have included Western companies. The primary Naxalite group is represented by the Communist Party of India (Maoist). The party's regional affiliates are active in the states of Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, Chhattisgarh, Bihar, Jharkhand, and West Bengal. Most recently, there has been significant Naxalite activity in the southern part of the state of Chhattisgarh. Restricted Areas: Certain parts of India are designated as "restricted areas" by the Indian Government, and require special advance permission to visit. These areas include:

- The state of Mizoram,
- The state of Manipur,
- The state of Arunachal Pradesh,
- The state of Nagaland,
- The state of Sikkim,
- Portions of the state of Himachal Pradesh near the Chinese border,
- Parts of the state of Uttarakhand (Uttaranchal) near the Chinese border,
- Portions of the state of Rajasthan near the Pakistani border,
- Portions of the state of Jammu & Kashmir near the Line of Control with Pakistan,
- The Andaman & Nicobar Islands,
- The Union Territory of the Laccadives Islands (Lakshadweep), and
- The Tibetan colony in Mundgod, Karnataka.

"Restricted Area Permits" can be obtained outside of India at Indian embassies and consulates abroad, or within India, from the Ministry of Home Affairs (Foreigners Division) at Jaisalmer House, 26 Man Singh Road, New Delhi. The states of Mizoram,

Manipur, Nagaland, Arunachal Pradesh, and Sikkim all maintain official guesthouses in New Delhi, each of which also can issue Restricted Area Permits for their respective states for individual travellers. Tourists also should exercise caution while visiting Mamallapuram (Mahabalipuram) in Tamil Nadu as the Indira Gandhi Atomic Research Center, Kalpakkam, is located just south of the site and is not marked as a restricted and dangerous area.

CRIME: Petty crime, especially theft of personal property, is common, particularly on trains or buses. Pickpockets can be very adept, and women have reported having their bags snatched, purse-straps cut, or the bottom of their purses slit without their knowledge. Theft of U.S. passports is quite common, particularly in major tourist areas, on overnight trains, and at airports. Train travellers are urged to lock their sleeping compartments and take valuables with them when leaving their berths. Air travellers are advised to carefully watch their bags in the arrival and departure areas outside of airports. Violent crime, primarily directed against foreigners, has traditionally been uncommon, although in recent years there has been a modest increase. U.S. citizens, particularly women, are cautioned not to. Travelers should be aware of several other scams that have been perpetrated against foreign travellers, particularly in Goa, Jaipur, and Agra. The scams generally target younger travellers and involve suggestions that money can be made by privately transporting gems or gold (both of which can result in arrest) or by taking delivery abroad of expensive carpets, supposedly while avoiding customs duties. The scam artists describe profits that can be made upon delivery of the goods and require the traveller to pay a “deposit” as part of the transaction. The items are always fake, and if they were real, the traveller could be subject to arrest.